

Logger Notes

* CJC and Temp headings on Raw Data files are switched. (Temp Should be in Column C)

Warm up tests:

Data File	Logger Start Time	Logger Stop Time	Comments
Data23	11:56:00	11:57:05	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data24	12:15:05	12:16:05	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data25	12:24:15	12:25:45	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor

Troubleshooting thermocouple:

Data File	Logger Start Time	Logger Stop Time	Comments
Data26	12:35:50	12:36:32	Tested a thermocouple not connected to the brakes Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data27	12:47:40	12:48:45	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data28	13:30:05	13:53:15	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor Ran a CBD test
Data29	14:47:55	14:48:30	Connected Driver Side Thermocouple No pressure sensor connected
Data30	14:53:22	14:54:28	Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple No pressure sensor connected

Cycle Tests:

Data File	Logger Start Time	Test Start Time	Test Stop Time	Logger Stop Time	Comments
Data31	15:02:25	15:04:04	15:14:37	15:15:25	CBD test 1 HCM logger fell out
Data32	15:17:40	15:18:39	15:28:00	15:29:15	CBD Warm Up Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data33	15:29:45	15:30:43	15:58:50	15:59:45	CBDx3 Connected Passenger Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor
Data34	16:15:45			16:17:51	Connected Driver Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure Sensor Quick test to view data is recording
Data35	16:21:00	16:21:44	17:14:49	17:15:45	UDDSx3 Connected Driver Side Thermocouple Connected Passenger Side Pressure

Sensor